

Classroom Management Practice and Human Security Development at Secondary School levels of Education in Nigeria: Issues and Prospects

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Abstract

This paper examines Classroom Management Practice and Human Security Development at Secondary School Levels of Education in Nigeria: Issues and Prospects. The state of classroom management Practice and security development in Nigeria were explored to present the current issues. Furthermore, various factors contribute to the current issues, and strategies should be employed to improve the situation. The paper also examines the role of educational management as it affects human security at the secondary level of education. It also emphasized the need to provide effective classroom management practices for better academic achievement among the students, thereby improving human security development at the secondary school level of education in Nigeria. Furthermore, the paper's strategies and policy approaches should be adopted in addressing challenges faced by students at the secondary school level of education in Nigeria. The paper concludes by suggesting that a combination of appropriate resources and targeted initiatives can help foster greater classroom management practice and human security development at the secondary level of education in Nigeria.

Keywords: Classroom Management Practice, Human Security Development, Issues, and Prospects

Introduction

Secondary school education is the phase of education students receive after primary school and before tertiary education. It serves as the link between primary and tertiary education as well as providing the opportunity for a child to acquire additional knowledge, skills, and traits beyond the primary level. Secondary education helps to inspire students with the desire for self-improvement and the achievement of excellence; it raises a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others, and respect the dignity of labor (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). However, it appears that classroom management practices well achieved will enhance quality education at the secondary school level.

Classroom management practice is a process that teachers use to ensure that classroom lessons run smoothly without disruptive behaviour from students compromising the delivery of instruction. At the secondary school level of education, it embraces all human endeavours that enable secondary school learners to fit into society. Although the process has changed over time as a result of situations, all the activities that are happening around the world are products of classroom management practice once it is successfully managed. One of the largest organizations in the world is education, which provides services that affect everyone in society. Formal and informal education affect the lives of the living. It is the foundation of all mankind. Consequently, much faith has been placed in formal education because of the role it plays in human security by creating awareness. Lack of respect for the authority of teachers and others in disciplinary acts threatens the teachers and the rights of other students and generally affects the quality of secondary school education in Nigeria (Ike, 2015). This is because teachers are disrespected and abused by both parents and students in the school, and in some cases, the principal does not provide protection for their teachers. Increasingly, students are victimized in schools by fellow students, teachers, cultists, and kidnappers. The success or failure of human security lies in their educational system, which depends on effective classroom management practices.

According to Onuorah and Nwankwo (2020), advanced nations of the world have attained a high level of social, economic, scientific, and technological advancement through well-planned and implemented educational systems. These are the cardinal and crucial factors that determine the success or failure of educational plans. It can also be defined as the actions teachers take to establish and sustain an environment that fosters students' academic achievement as well as their social, emotional, and moral growth. Classroom management has the final say in determining the pace of implementation of policies and plans aimed at realizing the educational target for human security. Human security management practices are aspects of security management that deal with the use of human beings in preventing and combating security threats (Onuorah & Nwankwo, 2020). Human security can be seen as the focus shifting to protecting individuals in every aspect of human endeavours, this also applies to students in the classroom.

The important dimensions are to entail the wellbeing of individuals and respond to ordinary people's needs in dealing with threats. Also, human security is the security of the people rather than the state. In the classroom setting,

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human security is the protection of the learners and the learning environment. Since teachers use classroom management to achieve positive learning outcomes that affect learners positively, A teacher with complete control over the classroom is an added advantage over human security in the classroom and the surrounding environment. Classroom management practice entails and argues that teachers should be trained thoroughly in all aspects of the topic, including the security of students in the classroom during lesson delivery. It assumes that teachers' inability to deal effectively with student misbehaviour stems from the fact that most of the training courses in the area focused on one or a few aspects. Research on staff development suggests that to implement new material into their own classrooms, teachers need both a solid theoretical understanding of the material and practice in specific methods or strategies (Ko & Rossen, 2020). There are five major factors or skill areas that are associated with classroom management security practice as outlined by Ko and Rossen (2020, P. 26) as below;

1. Classroom management should be based on solid understanding of current research and theory in classroom management and on students' personal and psychological needs.
2. Classroom management depends on establishing positive teacher-student and peer relationships that help students' basic psychological needs.
3. Classroom management involves using instructional methods that facilitate optimal learning by responding to the academic needs of individual students and the classroom group.
4. Classroom management involves using organizational and group management methods that maximize on-task student behaviour.
5. Classroom management involves the ability to use a wide range of counselling and behavioural methods that involve students in examining and correcting their inappropriate behaviour.

Management is also seen as a systematic process of organising both human and non-human resources in an organization to achieve its goals and objectives. According to Peretomode in Mgbodile (2014), classroom management is disturbed by the preparation and invention of educational policies and programmes to achieve educational goals. The importance of classroom management in secondary school cannot be neglected. It is with effective and efficient management that an organization or institution can plan, organize, staff, control, direct, and coordinate its activities to achieve predetermined goals. The aim of any teacher is to create the environment in such a way that individual learners will contribute for themselves in a good atmosphere for human security. All these are based on proper classroom management to succeed and fit into the improved security of the classroom in schools since secondary school is the pre-request to enter university education.

Classroom Management System at Secondary Schools Level

Classroom management at secondary school levels is concerned with defining goals in the organisation, for future direction and determining the mission and resources to achieve those targets. Planning is very important in any organization. The task of any manager in any organisation whether school or otherwise, is to identify the mission of the organisation and achieve its objectives. In the world of management, planning is important because it prepares organisations for the future by assessing what the organization wants to accomplish and how it will go about it.

Educational planning involves the application of rational, systematic analyses to the process of educational development with the aim of making education more effective and efficient in responding to the needs and goals of students and society (Oboegbulem 2014). This also involves taking decisions for future action with the view of achieving the objectives of education through optimum use of resources. Educational planning in Nigeria so far has been criticized for failing to anticipate the escalating costs of human insecurity as a result of educated unemployed people, among others. Educational management and planning have adopted some educational approaches to help achieve the role of human security in the country.

Educational planning takes place at two major levels: the national or state levels and the local or institutional levels. When planning is at the national or state level, it is referred to as planning at the macro level. This type of planning shows the fundamental aspects of educational development, such as educational reforms, educational financing, and manpower development (Ike, 2015). Planning at the local level is referred to as micro or grassroots. This type of planning is concerned with planning educational problems at the local level so that the local level can benefit from them. The role of educational planners is therefore to achieve human security through adequate planning of education. Thus, once education plans are made, effective implementation becomes very necessary in order to achieve them. According to UNESCO (2014), preparation of a comprehensive classroom management is therefore very important to reflect on the following:

1. Will the prepared plan be implemented at secondary school effectively, or once adopted, Will it be forgotten?
2. Will there be enough human and technical resources to carry them out at the secondary level?

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3. Will the commitments taken by the present government be respected by the future administrators at secondary schools in Nigeria?
4. Will the financial resources allocated to secondary schools be properly utilized?

It is the responsibility of educational management to ensure that plans are effectively implemented by using their knowledge to plan, organize, direct, control, and coordinate all activities in the classroom. In this view, Babalola (2016) sees educational management as the ability to handle carefully what goes on in the process of educating people. Based on his statement, educational management is therefore seen as being synonymous with strategizing, planning, organizing, running, governing, and supervising the entire process of teaching and learning that takes place at all levels of the educational system. Therefore, the functions of managers in the classroom or any organization are to plan, organize, direct, supervise, and evaluate men and human resources in the organisation to achieve its goals.

Planning at the secondary school level is very important in any organisation. To plan is to decide in advance what is to be done and how to do it. The classroom is power-house in which the success or failure of the learning process is generated and also sustained. The expectations and objectives of secondary education are normally accomplished more effectively in the classroom environment than anywhere else through very good human security, and this can occur through effective classroom management. The scarcity of resources makes these needs more pressing since the few available resources must be utilized to their fullest. The aim of any manager in any organisation is to identify the mission of the organisation or school and to set the objectives (Sullivan, 2014). The teacher in the classroom will then identify different strategies by which to achieve the agreed mission and objective by using classroom management and planning to achieve human security. Schools and human security are people centred. Therefore, the managers in the school system use effective classroom management and planning to achieve effective human security.

Classroom management means a place where students assemble for the purpose of teaching and learning. It is a very important place in the area of schoolwork. It holds the students together and gives them ample chance for group socialization by way of interacting with one another. It is a place where educational plans are carried out. Since secondary school has just one salient and overriding purpose, that is preparing the learners to fit into society or prepare them for the next stage of education, which is university. In other words, the classroom environment should be conducive to teaching, learning, and human security. The activities are already available; an action is needed to activate them into plans to achieve the set objectives. (Sullivan, 2014)

The teacher at the secondary school level needs to direct the implementation of classroom management plans and should provide a leadership style that will enable him to involve the learners in group activities and delegate duties and responsibilities to pupils to achieve the goals of the organisation. In order to achieve human security through classroom management at the secondary school level of education, all human and material resources should be well directed to achieve the set aims and objectives. The manager will need to supervise the work that is being done, ensuring that activities are carried out in line with agreed standards and taking steps to correct errors. Therefore, the work of effective classroom management and planning for human security is to help supervise the activities of students, resource materials, non-teaching staff, and the environment to ensure that secondary school objectives are achieved.

Evaluating is the final part of the management cycle, which assesses the results and measures them against the set goals and objectives. Therefore, the performance of the teachers in classroom management and planning is needed to ensure effective human security. Furthermore, Zubag and Soltis (2015) pointed out that education itself is essentially a moral undertaking because 'it is concerned with the development of human beings and human interactions.

Human Security and Classroom Management at Secondary School Level of Education

Human Security Development (HSD) is an interdisciplinary approach to addressing the needs of individuals and communities that focuses on reducing vulnerabilities and enhancing protections, enabling them to better access their rights and participate in society. Such measures can also be enhanced at the secondary school level. It is a holistic vision of development that seeks to build a more secure, just, and prosperous world by tackling the global and local causes of insecurity. HSD focuses on the interdependent and interconnected dimensions of individuals, communities, states, and the international system. It is a people-centred approach that pays particular attention to vulnerable and marginalized learners. The key pillars of HSD, according to Carpenter et al. (2018), show that there are:

1. Rights: Ensuring that all individuals and communities have access to their legal rights and can access the same opportunities and protections, regardless of gender, race, class, religion, or any other form of social class
2. Well-being: Enhancing the welfare of individuals and communities through improved access to health care, education, economic opportunities, and social needs
3. Security: Protecting individuals and communities from physical and psychological harm from crime, violence, and other forms of insecurity at the secondary school level

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4. Governance: Building stronger, more transparent, and accountable governance systems that promote the rule of law and respect for human rights can be enhanced at the secondary school level of education.
5. Sustainable Development: Promoting sustainable and equitable development plans for secondary school students that prioritize the environment, justice, and equality in schools

HSD sets out to create a more resilient and secure world by addressing the root causes of insecurity, poverty, and injustice. It is a cross-cutting approach that works to create conditions of justice and prosperity free from violence, inequality, and insecurity.

Ensuring Effective Classroom Management Practice for Human Security

The key administrative processes that help educational administrators achieve effective classroom management include planning, organising, staffing, directing, coordinating, reporting, and budgeting (POSDCRB) (Mgbodile 2014). However, administrative processes can be viewed as the sum total of the various processes of planning, organising, stimulating, coordinating, communicating, and evaluating, which aid administrators in the utilization of resources in the achievement of organisational goals (Ogboannya 2013), as illustrated in fig 1.

Fig 1: illustration of the administrative process

To plan is to decide what to do. The scarcity of resources makes planning important. The objective of planning is to utilize the available resources to achieve an objective. This means that planning is taking future decisions on how to implement the available resources to achieve goals such as human security at the secondary school level by engaging the community security architecture and giving them financial support in order to keep the school environment safe (Mgbodile 2014). In order to prevent conflict, human security is a human right; it refers to the security of the people and communities as opposed to the security of the state, which can be enhanced right from the secondary school level. Who is to plan? In the context of the school system, every school programme and activity should be planned. Since planning is not exclusively the responsibility of any person, For instance, within the educational system, the classroom teacher, the head teacher, the chairman of the school board, the minister of education, and any other person connected to the education sector are expected to be involved in one type of planning or another. Furthermore, in a classroom setting, for example, the teachers are involved in planning lesson notes, making classroom arrangements for pupils, and organizing field trips. Yohana (2019) has put forward a number of suggestions to make effective plans, Firstly, such a plan should identify the programmes to be implemented as well as the goals to be achieved. Secondly, the strategies and resources for achieving the objectives must be clearly spelled out. Thirdly, administrators should endeavour to involve as many teachers as possible in formulating and implementing plans, since people tend to avoid implementing plans they did not help formulate. Finally, plans should be flexible to accommodate changes at any point in time.

Organizing in classroom management, educational administrators can function or operate without the assistance of other people and the learners, so in order to achieve the set secondary objectives, the administrator must have a structure or framework for his school on which posts are created and assigned to subordinates and students. For example, within the secondary school setting, there is always a structure on which such posts as those for the head-teacher, assistant head-teacher, sectional heads, guidance counselor, classroom teacher, and monitors are created.

Therefore, organisation in school means having a structure in the school, creating posts on the structure, and assigning people to the posts for the purposes of performing specific duties (Yohana, 2019). The need for organising is for people to cooperate in the achievement of secondary school goals. Therefore, where duties are organised in such a manner, it leads to efficiency and human security. Coordinating: Administrators who are charged with the

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responsibility of utilizing resources in secondary schools need to have the ability to coordinate these resources in order to achieve their goals. Chatfield (2020) sees coordinating as a “process of fitting together the various groups and operations into an integral pattern”. Effective classroom management at the secondary school level needs proper coordination in order to achieve human security.

The Challenges of Classroom Management at Secondary School

A planner is expected to forecast, but his forecasting sometimes has errors. To avoid errors in forecasting, one has to work with all the data that is being used before one can really appreciate the value of the forecast made. This means that accurate data must be available before one can forecast to avoid errors of any kind. Furthermore, plans can be exposed to all sorts of fortunes and misfortunes; that is to say, some plans that were designed for one particular time may not be good enough for other situations at the secondary school level in Nigeria. This may be because of the constant changes in the social, cultural, and economic situation of the environment. Another challenge that classroom planners and managers face is the management of the school system. The secondary school system is composed of four interest groups. They include employees, stockholders, customers, and society. In this situation, management tries to figure out which group to serve first to ensure that one person's interests do not overshadow another person's to protect human security.

One major problem that affects classroom management and planning in Nigeria or any other country in the world is an unsteady political environment. There have been lots of changes in the government of Nigeria since independence, which means that old policies will be changed and the new government will initiate new ones. First Nigerian Republic, (2014) The new policies for secondary schools may be sound, but they will affect the educational plans since the new government may not consult their implementers at an early stage, which will affect the masses. Whatever affects the masses should affect the government.

Nigeria has had an unsteady economy since independence, which has affected the financial resources and the effectiveness of classroom management and planning to achieve human security in the country (Ogbonnaya, 2021). The good idea of the federal government and some state governments to initiate a policy to establish universities, upgrade colleges of education, and carry out new projects for their citizens is trapped due to inadequate financial resources. Some states in Nigeria, for example, Abia, Enugu, Cross-River, LMO, and Anambra, are willing to embark on policies for free education but cannot do so as a result of inadequate financial resources (Yohanna, 2019). So with inadequate financial resources, the educational planners are handicapped because they cannot plan for the future. (Ogbonnaya, 2021)

According to Ogbonnaya (2010), the ministries of education at both the federal and state levels hardly involve school administrators, teachers, and other school personnel in the planning process. This seriously affects effective classroom management and planning in secondary schools. Ogbonnaya (2010) condemned the act whereby school teachers and parents are hardly involved in the planning that involves the education sector. This means that effective educational planning and management suffer setbacks in their roles to achieve human security.

The way forward on classroom management practice and human security in secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Based on the challenges faced by classroom management in secondary schools' level the way forward, are as follows:

1. There should be a re-orientation in order to have strong consciousness and commitment towards our classroom management and to train adequate manpower for the creation of awareness for human security.
2. There should be proper funding of secondary education by the government, non-governmental organisations, private individuals, parents, and the society at large to incorporate educational management and planning at all levels of education.
3. Furthermore, the government should make it compulsory to train and retrain workers at secondary school level by organising workshops, conferences, and seminars for all classroom managers and planners since they coordinate human and material resources that are in charge of human security.
4. There should be a steady government to enable effective classroom management at secondary school level so that when they plan or formulate plans, they can last for years before changes are made. Much can be achieved with a steady political environment, good roads, an adequate food supply, a high cost of living, an adequate water supply, and resources utilized for development, thereby reducing human insecurity.
5. The federal, state, and local governments should provide adequate financial resources to the secondary schools in order to make them standards that can globally compete.
6. Also, the provision of adequate financial resources to secondary schools will enable the government to motivate these planners to do their best in managing human and material resources for achieving sustainable human security.

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Conclusion

Effective classroom management should involve controlling human and material resources. The proper management of these resources will enhance sustainable economic development, which will increase the standard of living in the country by the year 2030. African nations and especially the Nigerian government should increase their spending on training more educational planners so as to produce a more educated labour force capable of managing classrooms. Human security forms an important part of people's well-being, which is the function of the manager in an organisation. Insecurity cuts life short and threatens the human potential to achieve its objectives. It also has an adverse effect on students, especially at the secondary school level, thereby reducing the amount of manpower that will contribute to the growth of the economy.

Recommendations

1. There should be a steady government to enable educational planners to complete their projects, which means continuity in the implementation of educational plans by any government in power. in order to standardize secondary school education in Nigeria.
2. Nigeria should invest in the training of more educational planners since they are the bedrock of the country, manage the country's resources, and plan to use them to achieve the target goals. of secondary schools
3. Funds should be made available to secondary schools for the purpose of equipping the classrooms for effective teaching and learning to take place to enable human security.

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